

TOWARDS 21ST CENTURY CITIZENSHIP THROUGH SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Since learning, literacy, and life skills have become essential for individuals in the information age, the focus on education has shifted to preparation of students for the knowledge society. This is valid for all levels and spheres of education including but not limited to foreign language teaching in higher education. With this in mind, a new English for Academic Purposes (EAP) Course aiming to equip freshman level university students with necessary learning skills has been launched. A particular emphasis has been given to developing the students' English language skills so as to facilitate their communicative competence both in their academic and professional lives. The course adopts a challenge-based learning approach, which provides students with a meaningful framework for learning as it is based on solving real-world problems. In the course, the students work on real world challenges based on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations (UN) while using the learning skills (the four C's) of the 21st Century, namely critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication. During the course, the students work together on the issues highlighted as challenges in United Nation's report on Turkey's state regarding the 17 SDGs, and offer solutions in groups in the form of poster presentations, academic papers and oral presentations. The course has been implemented since fall 2021. In this concept paper, the researchers will share their experiences and research plans about the evaluation of the course based on Stufflebeam's Context (C), Input (I), Process (P), Product (P) (CIPP) Evaluation Model.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 21st Century Skills

The integration of 21st century skills in education has changed the nature of teaching and learning to a large extent. The replacement of conventional teaching methods with a new focus on the essential skills of the information age has led to the emergence of new practices in teaching that aim at fostering student engagement. When literature in the field is examined, it is found that all levels of education give importance to learning, literacy and life skills in their curriculum.

Due to a surplus of information and the possibility of easy access, the 21st century is agreeably called the age of information and technology. The ease to reach information and the infinite sources to have knowledge about a particular subject may sound to the advantage of individuals and societies that aspire for progress, yet it should also be noted that analyzing, interpreting and evaluating this abundance of information is much more vital to make optimum use of it. Knowing how to use information rather than reaching it has become a required skill, thereby making the integration of 21st century skills into every sphere of life essential. Moreover, the changing conditions of the world, economic structures, and social dynamics must also be taken into account. As Voogt and Rublin (2010) also discuss in their paper, the nature of jobs are changing and young people are educated for the jobs that do not even exist today, which requires individuals to compete globally while working both individually and in groups (Jacobson-Lundaberg, 2016). It would not be wrong to argue that teaching 21st century skills to young people will prepare societies for a future they cannot fully grasp.

1.2 Higher Education and 21st Century Language Teaching

The first category of 21st century skills, learning skills, are adopted in language education for the sake of a more integrated approach to teaching in higher education. Fostering the interaction of students through group work, which necessitates collaboration and communication, as well as developing their oral and written competencies with individual assignments that require creative thinking and creativity, 4Cs-oriented language teaching responds to the needs of 21st century university students. The emphasis on 21st century skills in language education also reflects the premise that individuals express themselves through language and language learning plays a key role in “professional success” as it gives one insight about the presence of different cultures and global issues (Cruz & Orange, 2016, p.2). A comprehensive language education, which encompasses all aspects of 21st century skills will ultimately give university students from different backgrounds the chance to work collaboratively and have a sense of teamwork. This will in turn develop their communicative skills as they will feel more self-confident seeing that they can communicate with people in a non-native language. Feeling the need to listen attentively in order to understand, thinking critically to make sense of what is said and giving an appropriate response to continue the conversation will develop communicative skills like listening, respecting different ideas and having empathy. In

other words, teaching the language of another culture will both necessitate and develop the use of 21st century skills.

1.3 21st Century Skills for Global Citizenship and Challenge-Based Learning (CBL)

An emphasis on 21st century skills in language education inevitably paves the way for the discussion of global issues in the classroom. Cruz and Orange argue that “21st century interdisciplinary themes” are used as subjects in language classrooms to develop academic language competency of students (2016, p.2). Discussing global problems as varied as and not limited to climate change, gender inequality, decent work, and sustainable energy both orally and in writing assignments gives students a new perspective to look at the global challenges countries are faced with contributing to their global citizenship competencies. In this respect, adopting challenge-based learning (CBL) as a pedagogical approach in language teaching in higher education makes it possible to engage students in real-life scenarios by using a secondary language to understand and discuss it.

Defining CBL as “extended problem-based learning”, Baloian et al draw attention to its project-based aspect. In 21st century language classrooms, the attempts to foster students’ collaborative and communicative skills as well as creativity through group projects become more meaningful when real life challenges are included as subject materials in courses. Similarly, Quieng et al argue that teaching 21st century skills to students enables them to be aware of global challenges, which will in turn help them endure difficult conditions and turn challenges into advantages (2015). With this objective in mind, language teaching with a challenge-based approach will equip students with necessary skills to respond to the needs of the era and fulfill the standards of the 21st century learning framework. A student who can think critically, communicate and collaborate in another language will also develop these skills further to conduct research, analyze and interpret information in the target language. Able to express themselves about social, economic and environmental issues in their native and non-native languages, students will also feel motivated to take active part in decision-making mechanisms, a skill which is formally defined as “civic engagement” and considered one of the liabilities of socially responsible universities of the 21st century world.

1.4 Challenge-Based Learning through Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Higher Education

One way of applying challenge-based learning in higher education is discussing global issues in a systematic way with real-life scenarios as course materials. With this purpose in mind, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations (UN), may be used as the context of lectures. Since their launch in 2015, the SDGs have been addressed in various settings such as strategic plans of institutions and companies, political agendas of policy makers, theoretical framework of many scientific studies and the curricula of educational institutions. The emphasis of the UN on active citizenship and inclusive societies has been adopted in education as

the basis to raise a more conscious and responsible youth with a new understanding of their role as decision-makers and drivers of change. Sustainability studies envision that collective action and learned practices for a more sustainable world have a recreative power. Dlouha et al emphasize the necessity of implementing an understanding of individual competences through SDGs in higher education (2019). In language education, SDGs function as the intercultural context in which the students are expected to have an understanding of sustainability practices in different countries. Using the target language as a tool to have debates about global challenges, do research about sustainability solutions and write reflective papers to propose their suggestions are all examples of practices for sustainability education. Indeed, a sustainability-oriented course enables the instructor to carry challenge-based learning a step further by fostering self-learning and contributing to enhancement of students' civic participation.

Although sustainable development has remained on the agenda for engineering disciplines for a long time, the broadening of the concept in the form of Sustainable Development Goals to other disciplines in higher education is a relatively new form of implementation. This is doubled by the need of integration of 21st century skills and competencies into classes to cater for the requirements of the new era. To this end, this concept paper will evaluate a relatively new course aiming at improving engineering students' academic English skills through content focusing on SDGs and equipping students with 21st century learning skills. A particular curriculum evaluation methodology will be applied for the evaluation of the course and the paper will seek responses to the following research questions: (i) What is the context behind the implementation of the course? (ii) What forms of input are available for the course? (iii) What is the process used during the operation of the course?

2 EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

Ornstein and Hunkins define curriculum development as a process comprising not only planning, implementation, and evaluation, but also people, processes and procedures (2003). It entails a dynamic relationship between the objectives, content, learning-teaching process and assessment elements of the education program where a change in one of those components affects all dimensions in the system. Curriculum is developed by designing, implementing, evaluating and reorganizing educational programs based on a needs analysis or program evaluation study, which can be defined as the decision-making process regarding the effectiveness of the program in reaching the predetermined goals and objectives. Using models in evaluation guides the evaluator not only about the kind of data that will be collected, but also when, where, and how the data collection process will take place. Without an underlying theory, the evaluator will seem to be working in the dark and will not be able to attribute the results to the program.

Figure 1. Key Components of the CIPP Evaluation Model and Associated Relationships with Programs (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014, p.318)

The evaluation model first developed by Stufflebeam, CIPP, which is an acronym for four types of evaluation: Context, Input, Process, and Product, was used during the design and evaluation of the course in this study. As depicted in Figure 1 above, while context evaluation aims to identify needs with the purpose of deciding on program goals, input evaluation is conducted to design plans involving the strategies and designs. In the process evaluation, shortcomings in a current program are explored and actions to revise implementation are taken, and product evaluation measures outcomes so as to decide about the revision or continuation of the program (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). Moreover, as cited in Christie and Alkin (2013), the CIPP model defines evaluation as a cyclical practice, rather than a product, which needs to be based on a carefully designed, but flexible process. In accordance with the CIPP methodology, the specific questions that the study seeks responses to are provided below:

Context	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the needs of the 21st century engineering student? 2. What are the aims, goals, and objectives of the course aligned with the context dimension of the CIPP model?
Input	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the resources and materials used in the course? 2. What strategies and activities have been used to address the needs of the students? 3. What forms of assessment have been implemented?
Process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To what extent are the planned activities carried out and is there a need for adjustments or revisions of the course? 2. How do the instructors perceive the course materials and teaching methods? 3. How is the teaching and learning process affected during the implementation of the course?

3 EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

In accordance with the aforementioned evaluation model (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014), *English for Academic Purposes (EAP) through Global Goals Course*, which has been implemented at Istanbul Technical University (ITU) School of Foreign Languages (SFL) for two consecutive academic terms, will be evaluated elaborating on Context, Input and Process dimensions. The Product dimension of the CIPP model will be finalized after the complete set of data is collected as part of continuous quality improvement process.

3.1 Context

Regarding the context evaluation, firstly literature on sustainable engineering and the needs of the 21st century engineers was reviewed. Sustainability is a concept referring to a future that balances societal, environmental, and economic issues with the aim of achieving a higher standard of living. Hence, society, environment, culture, and economy are all interwoven components of sustainable development, which cannot be considered separately. Similarly, based on the report titled *Engineering for Sustainable Development: Delivering on the Sustainable Development Goals*, sustainable engineering adopts a multidisciplinary approach focusing on not only technical issues, but also social, political, and ethical ones while taking into account the whole system and the global context (UNESCO & ICEE, 2021). Thus, 21st century engineers have a critical role in solving global challenges related to such fields as energy, health care and environment. For this complex task, they need to adopt a multi-disciplinary approach while working in collaboration with culturally diverse teams, and develop complex communication skills. Consequently, curriculum and instruction in the 21st century integrates 21st century skills into core subjects and interdisciplinary themes, rather than focusing mostly on technical content. Based on the report of the American Association of Colleges for Teacher Education (AACTE) and the Partnership for 21st Century Skills, learning and innovation skills comprise critical thinking and problem solving, communication, collaboration, creativity and innovation, which are all to be constituent components of 21st century engineering curriculum (Greenhill, 2010).

Istanbul Technical University, which has a pioneering role in raising engineers in Turkey, is also one of the partners of the European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA), which “is the first alliance of Higher Education Institutions (graduate engineering schools, technology universities and full-spectrum universities) from different countries in Europe. It offers high-quality programs and courses in line with the objectives of the alliance, thereby contributing to its mission to transform European higher education while strengthening links between engineering and society by re-inventing the ‘European engineer’” (EELISA, 2022).

Moreover, in line with the mission of the University with its emphasis on contributing to a sustainable community, the School of Foreign Languages at ITU started to implement *EAP through Global Goals Course* for the first time in Fall 2021, so as to design language education conforming to the needs and priorities of engineering

students. It is offered as a 3-credit EAP course aiming to develop students' English language skills through 21st century core skills or the 4Cs (Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, Creativity) and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. As Mikhnenko and Absaliamova pointed out in their article, language education of engineers in the 21st century provides an open ground for "intellectualisation" (2018, p. 37). They argue that integrating language education with a special focus on EAP and ESP enables engineering students and specialists to develop basic skills that a professional needs such as creative and analytical thinking, communicating by using different languages and learning how to access information (2018). Not different from what Mikhnenko and Absaliamova suggest, the course at ITU also offers an academic and intellectual environment for the professionalization of engineering students. Among the objectives of the course are to enable students to express themselves using appropriate discourse strategies in written and spoken communication, to develop the 4 Cs (Critical thinking, Communication, Collaboration, Creativity) of 21st century Learning, which are core skills that the students will need in their academic and social lives, to enhance students' awareness regarding Sustainable Development Goals, to improve students' collaboration skills in multidisciplinary groups, and to develop associated academic practices and soft skills, such as goal-setting, self-reflection and time management.

3.2 Input

EAP through Global Goals Course has been taught online by 26 English language instructors to 999 first year students enrolled in various engineering departments since fall 2021. It has been offered as a compulsory course for students at a certain level of English proficiency. The textbook used in this course is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Non-commercial 4.0 International License, and it is in line with the goals and objectives defined in the syllabus. To supplement the textbook to be used in the program for the first time and to better serve the goals of the course, a unit on problem-solution paper writing has been integrated. Moreover, creative/critical thinking, and teamwork skills of students have been enhanced through a case study unit. Sample problem-solution and case study papers have been created and shared with students. To provide the instructors with background information related with SDGs and 21st century skills and learning, lesson presentations have been shared. During the course, the students have the chance to improve not only their English language skills, but also 21st century learning skills while reading, listening and responding to texts about the SDGs.

Concerning the assessments, the students are to prepare poster presentations on two related SDGs, attracting attention of the audience and providing solutions to a problem. The students are expected to perform this task in pairs, in compliance with the focus of the 21st century skills on communication and collaboration. The students are also expected to write a problem-solution paper on one of the challenges in the report by Sachs et al (2021) regarding the implementation of the SDGs, which has enabled them to critically tackle real life problems of their own countries and propose

solutions. To help them get acquainted with this kind of assessment, different from previously implemented formats, the students have been provided with sample problem-solution papers presenting the problem and suggesting alternative solutions. As final assessment, the students work in groups and write an essay analyzing a case scenario based on its relationship with the SDGs and deliver an oral presentation on it. As underlined in *A Core Inventory for General English (British Council/EAQUALS)*, using real life scenarios in language teaching enables the students to evaluate a particular situation using the target language and develop new perspectives by providing a “holistic setting” (North et al., 2015). Within this scope, this assessment has contributed to the students’ ability to work in teams as well as enhancing their critical thinking and communication skills contributing to their development of new perspectives. With regard to the input of the course, it is obvious that students have solution suggestions to global issues ranging from climate crisis, gender inequality, global hunger to water sanitation, education rights and innovative cities, indicating improvement in their awareness of the SDGs as a consequence of implementation of the course.

3.3 Process

As Stufflebeam emphasizes, the most foundational principle of the CIPP model is “not to prove, but to improve” (cited in Stufflebeam and Coryn 2014, p. 176). With an aim to develop the course, certain steps have been taken. For instance, since fall 2021, feedback on course materials and assessments has been collected from the instructors via an online platform. To collect feedback on course materials, the following two open-ended questions were asked: 1. What would you change in Unit XX next time you teach the Course? (pacing, videos, activities, supplementary materials, etc.?) 2. Would you like to add anything else? To collect feedback on assessments, the instructors were asked to write down their comments about each assessment’s guidelines and rubric. In addition, 30 minute informal discussions to share experiences, i. e. what went good or bad, or ask questions, suggest changes were held online.

As a result of the feedback collected and online meetings, it was observed that most of the instructors felt their students needed more input and context on SDGs before starting to work on their first assessment, i. e. poster presentation. Consequently, in spring 2022, each student was assigned one of the 17 SDGs and asked to present the details of the goals and their targets and conduct a student-led discussion, which also gave the students the chance to improve their communication skills. Moreover, most of the instructors agreed that in line with the course objectives, the problem-solution paper regarding the SDGs that remain as challenges for Turkey should be an oral assessment rather than a written one, which is considered as one of the steps to be taken for improving course implementation due to the expected focus of the course on spoken communication rather than written language production to better cater for the needs of engineering students.

The fact that the course was not delivered in person and all these assignments and presentations were carried out online contributed to another objective of the course as well. Delivering online presentations using digital tools, doing online research and preparing posters with the help of various multimedia tools obviously fostered the digital literacy skills of students, which are also among the 21st century skills. Students were expected to use their critical thinking and problem-solving skills to complete online tasks. Considering that companies are employing their workers through online exams and interviews, dissertations are presented online in academia, and the number of webinars, open access courses, workshops as well as certificate/degree programs is rapidly increasing, the online delivery of a challenge-based course has enabled students to simultaneously use various skills. Considering that a challenge-based course addresses social and cultural dynamics that lead to important transformations in societies, a language course through SDGs cannot be given regardless of the changes in technology and the acceleration of digitalization. As Gómez-Zermeño also argues, Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) cannot be “prescriptive” particularly in the age of digital learning, highlighting the potential of digital learning to facilitate “active knowledge co-creation and communities of practice” (p.579). Online delivery of the course, in this respect, contributes to the objectives of 21st century challenge-based courses to provide ample ground to share information and experiences as well as resources, inviting students and instructors to contemplate how knowledge is created.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper presents the evaluation of the course *EAP through Global Goals* in accordance with CIPP model elaborating on Context, Input and Process dimensions. It captures the background for multiple criteria in the context of CIPP providing insight and reference points for implementation. The integration of Sustainable Development Goals, 21st century learning skills and challenge-based learning in higher education undoubtedly underpins the essentials of engineering education in the knowledge society as indicated in the scope of the study. Despite information provided concerning constituents of the evaluation model in the current study, this is still a work in progress and is to be completed by the next step in which structured feedback will be collected from students. The results will then be used so as to fine-tune the content as well as assessment of the course. Sustainable Development Goals and 21st century citizenship are a critical consideration in accordance with the requirements of the current era and involve further exploration in various fields of higher education.

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